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PACIFICUS

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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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"CHALK DUST AND COLD CASES"

I face the lines of eyes.

Their notebooks empty, their minds informed,
But something in me went a long time ago.
A flame that once, with passion, glowed.

The lectures are a rehearsed play,
I recite the words, then glance away.
Crime scenes, theories, minds to shape.
But to be honest, I've grown cold.

The justice I once aimed to impart.
Now it seems too far away, beyond reach.
Too many lies, too many files,
Too few reforms, too many trials.

I track the footsteps of shattered law.
Define the reason without the reason.
I mark their aspirations in slowly fading ink.
And struggle too much not to think.

Is this a vocation or a prison?
A textbook-bound on each page?
A badge I bear without faith
A vain promise, a silent sorrow.

Still, I do speak, for I must.
Though each word is lined with dust.
I hope that they listen to what I once understood.
That justice exists, if they seek.